

Short communication

Validation of the newly proposed Brighton Collaboration case definition for vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis

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ABSTRACT

Vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis (VITT) is a newly recognized syndrome mediated by anti-platelet factor 4 antibodies induced by Covid-19 adenovirus-vectored vaccines including ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 and Ad26.COV2.S. This study validated a proposed Brighton Collaboration case definition for VITT. A data collection form was developed and used to capture the variations in VITT criteria and assess their level of diagnostic certainty from adjudicated positive VITT case datasets in Germany (n = 71), UK (n = 220), Australia (n = 203), and Taiwan (n = 56). We observed high prevalence of each component of the proposed VITT definition in positive cases (84%–100%), except for the occurrence of thrombosis or thromboembolism criterion in only 34% of VITT cases in Taiwan. The sensitivity of this proposed definition was 100% for Germany and UK, 92% for Australia, and 89% for Taiwan cases. These findings support the validity of this case definition for VITT.

1. Introduction

In 2021, multiple countries recognized a syndrome of concurrent thrombosis and thrombocytopenia in recipients of Covid-19 adenovirus-vectored vaccines (ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 and Ad26.COV2.S) [1–3]. In May 2021, the Brighton Collaboration developed a draft interim case definition for thrombosis with thrombocytopenia syndrome (TTS) for this new clinical entity; this interim TTS case definition was later updated in November 2021 based on evolving knowledge about this condition and its relationship to vaccines [4].

TTS encompasses many different entities with varying pathogenesis; one of those entities is vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis (VITT), which is now a clearly defined syndrome mediated by platelet activating anti-platelet factor 4 (PF4) antibodies induced by

at least the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 and Ad26.COV2.S vaccines [5,6]. In March 2023, a Brighton Collaboration TTS-VITT Case Definition Working Group was formed to consider a revision of the November 2021 TTS case definition. The Working Group proposed a VITT case definition in October 2023, based on criteria of thrombocytopenia, elevated D-dimer, acute or newly diagnosed thrombosis or thromboembolism, characteristic interval from vaccination to onset, and positive anti-PF4 antibody test, providing levels of diagnostic certainty (LOC) [7]. The classification in different LOCs depends on the availability of data and is partly determined by missing data; therefore, levels 1 (most specific but least sensitive; *definite* case), 2 (*probable* case), and 3 (least specific but most sensitive; *possible* case) LOC are considered as confirmed.

The Brighton Collaboration case definitions are intended to serve as a tool to enable standardized assessment and presentation of data

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collected in clinical trials, epidemiologic studies, and in adverse events following immunization surveillance systems both in high- and low-resource settings; they should be avoided from being used in unintended settings such as a clinical case management [8]. For implementation, a case definition can be evaluated regarding applicability, usefulness, reliability, sensitivity, specificity, and positive as well as negative predictive values. In this report we piloted an approach to (1) validate each criterion; (2) validate LOC; and (3) assess sensitivity of the proposed VITT definition.

2. Material and methods

Four sites contributed data from their existing VITT case datasheets: each in Germany, UK, Australia, and Taiwan. These datasheets already encompassed laboratory and imaging tests, and clinical information relevant to the proposed VITT case definition, for patients from previous studies [9–12], including (1) cases referred to the Greifswald laboratory with serologically confirmed VITT (positive anti-PF4 heparin enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay and/or positive functional test for platelet activating anti-PF4 antibodies); (2) definite and probable cases from the UK Expert Haematology Panel focused on VITT; (3) expert adjudicated cases from the Thrombosis and Haemostasis Society of Australia and New Zealand (THANZ) VITT Working Group; and (4) expert adjudicated VITT cases from Taiwan Covid-19 vaccine safety surveillance.

A data collection form was developed and used to capture the possible variations in VITT criteria and assess their LOC per draft definition from adjudicated true (positive) cases (Supplementary Tables S1 and S2). The site investigators (L. Schönborn, S. Pavord, H. Tran and W.-I. Huang) provided an aggregate number of cases in specific criterion subgroups, applied the case classification logic to their VITT cases [7], and recorded an aggregate number of cases meeting each specific LOC. The completed data collection forms were then returned to the corresponding author (W.-T. Huang) for analysis.

The following parameters were assessed descriptively: (1) prevalence of each component of the proposed VITT case definition in positive cases; (2) ability to assign LOC and reasons for being classified as level 4 and 5; and (3) sensitivity, calculated as the proportion of VITT cases assessed as levels 1–3 LOC (confirmed cases per Brighton Collaboration criteria).

3. Results

A total of 550 VITT cases were used to validate this proposed case definition: 71 from Germany (64 following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 and 7 following Ad26.COV2.S vaccines); 220 from UK and 203 from THANZ (all following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccines); and 56 from Taiwan (53 following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19, 2 following mRNA-1273, and 1 following MVC-COV1901 vaccines).

Table 1 summarizes the prevalence of each component of the proposed definition in these positive cases. Thrombocytopenia was the most prevalent criterion reported, occurring in 98%–100% of total VITT cases. The thrombosis or thromboembolism criterion, including cases with no evidence for thrombosis but severe persistent headache with onset on day 4 or later after vaccination, was met by 100% of cases from the UK and Germany, 90% of THANZ cases, but only 34% of the cases from Taiwan: 26 (46%) reported only supportive imaging finding instead of confirmed thrombotic events.

Nearly all the positive cases were assessable (levels 1, 2, 3 or 5) (Table 2); sensitivity of this proposed definition for VITT was 100% for German and UK, 92% for THANZ, and 89% for Taiwan cases. Sixteen (8%) cases in THANZ and 6 (11%) cases in Taiwan did not meet levels 1, 2, or 3 of certainty as they had either an alternative diagnosis for the illness (level 5 [not a case of VITT]), or presence of no more than 2 of the 5 VITT criteria (level 4 [insufficient information]).

Table 1

Prevalence of each component of the proposed VITT case definition in positive cases.^a

Component	Germany (n = 71)	UK (n = 220)	THANZ (n = 203)	Taiwan (n = 56)
<i>Thrombocytopenia</i>				
Platelet <150 × 10 ⁹ /L	63/66 (95)	217/ 218 (>99)	202/203 (>99)	56/56 (100)
Platelet below local laboratory lower limit for normal	65/66 (98)	217/ 218 (>99)	NA	NA
≥50% decreased from a previously documented count	1/66 (2)	NA	NA	NA
<i>Elevated D-dimer</i>				
Peak D-dimer >4000 ug/ml or >8 times UNL	50/53 (94)	190/ 202 (94)	180/202 (89)	47/56 (84)
<i>Thrombosis or thromboembolism</i>				
Thromboembolic event confirmed by pathology, surgical procedure or imaging	63/71 (89)	214/ 220 (97)	179/203 (88)	13/56 (23)
No evidence for thrombosis but had severe persistent headache with onset on day 4 or later after vaccination	8/71 (11)	6/220 (3)	4/203 (2)	6/56 (11)
<i>Characteristic interval from vaccination to onset</i>				
Onset day 4–30 after vaccination	71/71 (100)	207/ 218 (95)	173/202 (86)	48/56 (86)
Onset day 31–42 after vaccination in context of isolated DVT or pulmonary embolism	0/71 (0)	5/218 (2)	13/202 (6)	1/56 (2)
<i>Anti-PF4 antibody</i>				
Positive anti-PF4 antibody ELISA test	70/71 (99)	198/ 204 (97)	95/201 (47)	35/42 (83)
Positive functional assay for PF4 dependent antibodies	71/71 (100)	NA	123/195 (63)	3/3 (100)
<i>Alternative diagnosis</i>				
No alternative diagnosis found that explained clinical symptoms	71/71 (100)	220/ 220 (100)	187/203 (92)	56/56 (100)

VITT, vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis; THANZ, Thrombosis and Haemostasis Society of Australia and New Zealand; NA, not available; UNL, upper normal limit; DVT, deep vein thrombosis; PF4, platelet factor 4; ELISA, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.

^aData are presented as n/N (%), where n is the number of cases matching that criterion and N is the number of cases with data available for this criterion (% = 100 × n/N). Not all the positive VITT cases have contributed to the information required because either the diagnostic tests were not done, or relevant information or results were not gathered.

4. Discussion

This study validates each criterion and LOC of a newly proposed VITT case definition. We observed a high presence of key criteria and good sensitivity of the proposed definition in adjudicated positive cases. Although 66% of cases in Taiwan failed to meet the criterion for thrombosis or thromboembolism, this definition was still applicable and maintained reasonable sensitivity (89% classified as levels 1–3 LOC); three cases assigned VITT level 4 met TTS level 2 [7].

Improving the sensitivity of a case definition often comes at the

Table 2
Classification of positive VITT cases according to the proposed case definition.^a

Level of diagnostic certainty	Germany (n = 71)	UK (n = 220)	THANZ (n = 203)	Taiwan (n = 56)
Level 1				
Presence of all 5 VITT criteria	49 (69)	170 (77)	80 (39)	13 (23)
A positive functional assay for PF4 dependent antibodies and presence of 3 of the other 4 VITT criteria	22 (31)	0 (0)	37 (18)	2 (4)
Level 2	0 (0)	28 (13)	11 (5)	18 (32)
Level 3	0 (0)	22 (10)	59 (29)	17 (30)
Level 4	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	6 (11) ^c
Level 5	0 (0)	0 (0)	16 (8) ^b	0 (0)

VITT, vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis; THANZ, Thrombosis and Haemostasis Society of Australia and New Zealand; PF4, platelet factor 4; NA, not available; TTS, thrombocytopenia with thrombosis syndrome.

^aData are presented as n (%), where n is the case count of that row (% = 100 × proportion of n among total cases in each country datasheet).

^bThe 16 cases had alternative diagnoses that explained clinical symptoms.

^cThe 6 cases had presence of: thrombocytopenia + characteristic onset + NA anti-PF4 (n = 2); thrombocytopenia + characteristic onset + negative anti-PF4 (n = 1); thrombocytopenia + elevated D-dimer + negative anti-PF4 (n = 2); thrombocytopenia + NA anti-PF4 (n = 1). They were assessed as TTS level 2 (n = 3) or level 5 (n = 3).

expense of specificity. We assumed 100% specificity of this definition, as all the originally proposed LOCs require absence of alternative diagnosis to explain the clinical illness. The non-VITT control (negative) patients who have an alternative diagnosis would have been classified as level 5 (not a case of VITT). Of note, the subsequent revision has removed an alternative diagnosis as an exclusion criterion for level 1 VITT in the officially *published* Brighton Collaboration case definition [13]; the presence of a more plausible alternative explanation for the illness will exclude a diagnosis of VITT only for levels 2 and 3 LOC. This change would have resulted in one (6%) of the 16 level 5 THANZ cases being reclassified to level 1 LOC, but no notable alternation in the case definition sensitivity (93%). As a definitive diagnostic test for VITT does not exist, the cases that served as reference still could have been incorrectly adjudicated as true positive by local experts, and the magnitude of misclassification bias varied by site. Also, we did not validate the proposed definition using cases from low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) as few VITT cases have been reported from LMICs.

There was a marked difference between the proportion of confirmed thrombosis or thromboembolism events in Taiwan cases compared with those from other sites, whilst the other criteria were consistently reported across positive cases. In a recent multinational study by the Global Vaccine Data Network [14], the Taiwan population was observed to have a lower background incidence of pulmonary embolism, but not thromboses at unusual sites (e.g., cerebral venous sinus thrombosis), as compared to the populations from Australia, Canada, Denmark, France, and UK. Information for non-Taiwan cases were collected using active surveillance methodologies, and information collected for the Taiwan cases were from the national enhanced passive Covid-19 vaccine safety surveillance [12]. The VITT criterion for thrombosis or thromboembolism requires surgical, histopathologic, or radiologic confirmation [15]; details of the radiographic imaging (e.g., with vs without contrast) were often not available from the initial narrative reports, and surgical or pathologic findings were rarely described. Furthermore, follow-up reports often incompletely captured subsequent investigations and findings.

The creation, automation, and validation/evaluation of case definitions and rapid assessment tools in the companion guides are important for the success of new case definition lifecycle service in the *Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines* Project (SPEAC 2.0) to support the *100 Days Mission* articulated by the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI) [16,17]. The methods and data source(s) used in this study will be the standard approach to evaluate upcoming case definitions developed as part of SPEAC 2.0, ideally *before* they are finalized and published. This will hopefully address one of the common concerns and critiques of Brighton Collaboration case definitions. In this validation, positive VITT cases from Germany, UK, and THANZ were provided by the Working Group members who proposed the case definition, and there could be biases. The use of a 4th referent case datasheet from Taiwan, in which the provider (W.-I. Huang) was not involved in the development of this definition, eliminated these biases. Strategies to identify and engage potential data partners from the beginning of case definition development to map, align, and prepare such datasets in parallel will allow for timely validation. Further research into the performance of this and other already published case definitions (currently more than 70) should continuously assess not only sensitivity but also other measures in broader, real-world settings, prioritizing CEPI-relevant adverse events of special interest. Effective collaboration throughout the process of development, digitalization, and evaluation of standards and tools can provide synergies and conservation of resources for these data-dependent activities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Wan-Ting Huang: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Barbara Law:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Huyen Tran:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Linda Schönborn:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Wei-I Huang:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Jim Buttery:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Vivien Mun Yee Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Andreas Greinacher:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Sue Pavord:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: H. Tran reports project grant funding support outside of the submitted work from AstraZeneca and Sanofi. W.-I. Huang is a member of the national enhanced passive Covid-19 vaccine safety surveillance team in Taiwan. J. Buttery has served as an independent data monitoring committee member for CEPI SPEAC, GSK, Serum Institute of India, SK Biosciences and Clover Vaccines. His employer Murdoch Children's Research Institute is compensated for his time. A. Greinacher reports grants and non-financial support from Aspen, Boehringer Ingelheim, MSD, Bristol Myers Squibb (BMS), Paringenix, Bayer Healthcare, Gore Inc., Rovi, Sagent, Biomarin/Prosensa, personal fees from Aspen, Boehringer Ingelheim, MSD, Macopharma, BMS, Chromatec, Werfen, nonfinancial support from Boehringer Ingelheim, Portola, Ergomed, GTH e.V. outside the submitted work. No other authors report conflicts of interest.

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Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2024.07.032>.

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